

Comparison of calculated and measured paleo-sea level proxies with PaleoMIST 1.0, Report 1, version 2

Evan James Gowan

As a supplement to “*A new global ice sheet reconstruction for the past 80 000 years*” by Evan J. Gowan, Xu Zhang, Sara Khosravi, Alessio Rovere, Paolo Stocchi, Anna L. C. Hughes, Richard Gyllencreutz, Jan Mangerud, John-Inge Svendsen & Gerrit Lohmann

Report 1: Comparing six lower mantle models using the maximal MIS 3 scenario of PaleoMIST 1.0.

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1 Purpose of this document

In this report there is a detailed summary, including plots, of a worldwide compilation of paleo-sea level data, and six ice sheet-Earth models. In this particular report, we compare the standard version of PaleoMIST 1.0 (with 2500 year time steps and using a lower mantle viscosity of 4×10^{22} Pa s), with five other Earth models with viscosity values ranging between 10^{21} and 10^{23} . When developing PaleoMIST 1.0, a variety of lower mantle viscosity values were tested, and it was found that a value approaching 10^{23} Pa s provided the best trade-off between increasing the amount of ice in the center of the Laurentide Ice Sheet and fitting the sea level data. This ended up being true for the Eurasian ice sheets as well. PaleoMIST 1.0 was tuned to an Earth model with a viscosity of 4×10^{22} Pa s, but the comparison shown in this document demonstrate that a slightly higher value of 10^{23} Pa s provides an even better fit.

The accompanying paper is Gowan et al. (2021).

Note that earlier versions of this report used the minimal scenario of PaleoMIST 1.0, but I now prefer the maximal scenario. The load is now linearly interpolated to 500 year time steps, which should provide a more realistic representation of ice sheet evolution, and therefore reduce the loading effects in the time series.

2 Update history

This database has its beginnings as a way for me to evaluate ice sheet reconstructions. The first efforts were reported in Gowan et al. (2016), where I first created the scripts and scoring method that I continue to use. This was done in a fairly disorganized way, as it was made in haste without any illusions that it would be expanded into global database. The data used in Gowan et al. (2016) focused on northwestern Canada, but since I have changed the way I organize and assess the data, this is not included in the current database.

Later on, in order to refine the global ice sheet reconstruction reported in Gowan et al. (2021), I was forced by necessity to create a more organized database structure. I included data from Eastern Canada and North America, northern Europe and Asia, southeastern Asia, and a few additional sites that have data between 80,000 and 15,000 years ago. I still largely relied on the scripts and programs created in Gowan et al. (2016), but the plotting was automated to a certain degree. This was considered to be version 1.0 of the database. Further updates are described below.

2.1 Version 1.1: October 22, 2021

This document has been updated to include several additional sites at the LGM and MIS 3. It also has fixed an error in the Cairns and Mackay sites caused by incorrectly subtracting half of the depth range rather than adding it. I apologize for this error. For the coral data for Tahiti and Huon Peninsula, it was originally set to be marine limiting, since the living range was tens of meters. We now use the 2-sigma range determined by Hibbert et al. (2016). We include the interpretations of sea level range by Ishiwa et al. (2019) and Yokoyama et al. (2000) for the Bonaparte Gulf shallow marine/estuary/intertidal data in addition to my conservative marine limiting assignment. I also included the interpreted sea level of Huon Peninsula by de Gelder et al. (2022) for MIS 3 to compare with the coral depth range interpretation by Hibbert et al. (2016). Finally, I also recalibrated all the radiocarbon dates using updated calibration

curves published in 2020 (Heaton et al., 2020; Hogg et al., 2020; Reimer et al., 2020).

This update was used in the paper Gowan et al. (2022).

2.2 Version 1.2: March 14, 2022

I have included data from the Baltic Sea (Rosentau et al., 2021) and North Sea (Vink et al., 2007).

2.3 Version 1.3: July 4, 2022

In this update, data from Antarctica are included (Briggs and Tarasov, 2013; Ishiwa et al., 2021). I have also updated the figures so that index points are now drawn as rectangles, rather than the green dots as before. I have used different shades of green depending on whether or not the indicator uncertainty is below or above 10 m.

2.4 Version 2.0: April 19, 2023

This version represents a substantial revision of the database structure. A lot of the analysis and plotting code that was originally written in Bash and Fortran has been rewritten in Python. The map plots are now generated automatically (previously, I manually created the map boundaries). There is now a “scratch_datasets” folder, where I store the spreadsheets with the original data. The scripts in the scratch datasets folder will automatically create the subregions in the “sea_level_data” and extract the reservoir ages from the shapefiles in the GIS folder. The revised Marine20 calibration curve necessitated this move, as it invalidated the old reservoir ages. These changes means that the amount of time for upkeep and future data incorporation is substantially reduced.

This update includes data from Greenland and Australia. The Greenland data was largely compiled by myself, using the list by Lecavalier et al. (2014) as a starting point, but also including data not from that list. Notably, it includes the compilation of isolation basin based sea level indicators by Long et al. (2011). The data for Australia was largely derived from compilations by Lewis et al. (2013), Sloss et al. (2007), Belperio et al. (2002).

3 Summary of ice and Earth models

The main models included here are from PaleoMIST. This is a global ice sheet reconstruction at a very crude 2500 year time step. I have started to use a 500 year interpolated version, which should produce more accurate results in ice covered areas, though it makes less impact in far field regions.

For this document, I use PaleoMIST 1.0. The minimal MIS 3 configuration reconstruction is PM_1, while the maximal configuration is PM_1_A

For the Earth models, I created a shorthand scheme during my PHD, which I have continued to use. A full explanation can be found on the [github page](#):

https://github.com/evangowan/icesheet/blob/master/global/earth_model_format_codes.txt

The full description of each model compared in this document is in this section.

3.1 Ice models

PM_1_A_h - PaleoMIST 1.0 - full MIS 3 Laurentide Ice Sheet scenario, with Hudson Bay fully covered, and ice extent much larger. In this version, the sea level was calculated by linearly interpolating the ice load to 500 year time steps, which should mitigate some of the issues with overpredicting the loading in ice covered regions.

3.2 Earth models

ehgr - 120 km thick lithosphere, 4×10^{20} Pa s upper mantle, 4×10^{22} Pa s lower mantle

4 Paleo-sea level compilations

This is a list of paleo-sea level compilations, which served as the basis for this report. We acknowledge the hard work of the people compiling the data, as well as acknowledging those who collected the original data.

4.1 North America

- Eastern Canada - Vacchi et al. (2018)
- Hudson Bay - Simon et al. (2016)
- Greenland isolation basins - Long et al. (2008)
- Eastern United States north of Georgia - Engelhart and Horton (2012)

For eastern Canada, the database by Vacchi et al. (2018) referred just to compilations (such as Simon et al. (2016)) rather than the original sources. I have tried to track down the original sources as much as possible, but in some cases it was not possible. I made use of the compilations by Simon et al. (2016), Gowan et al. (2016) and an unpublished dataset by A.S. Dyke and T.S. James (some which was summarized in Dyke and Peltier (2000)) to track down references. Some were not listed in any of these compilations, so I had to track it down myself.

The MIS 3-5 data from the east coast of the United States was compiled by Pico et al. (2017).

Most of the data for Greenland was compiled by me, aside from the isolation basin dataset by Long et al. (2008). Though it did not contain a compilation of data, Lecavalier et al. (2014) listed references to a large number of studies that had sea level data. This was used to find the data used in this database. I also did a literature search for studies published after 2013.

4.2 Europe

- Baltic Sea - Rosentau et al. (2021)
- North Sea - Vink et al. (2007)

The Baltic Sea sea level indicators are from (Rosentau et al., 2021). Note that some of the regions that they designated were really large with the gradient of the GIA, so I made smaller regions. This is why the regions in this report do not correspond to theirs in many places. Also note that Rosentau *et al* chose to enter the radiocarbon dates for Ångermanland as pre-calibrated dates. I have not changed them.

The main compilation for the North Sea is by Vink et al. (2007). Though this predates the HOLSEA project, they use the indicative meaning concept and have a rigorous assessment of error, and is compatible with it. For Rotterdam, Netherlands, there is a HOLSEA compilation by Hijma and Cohen (2019). In Langeoog, there is a HOLSEA dataset by Bungenstock et al. (2021). I have also included HOLSEA formatted data from Norderney (Scheder et al., 2022). Western Denmark does not a HOLSEA formatted compilation, so I added data compiled by Gehrels et al. (2006) and Jessen et al. (2019).

4.3 Eurasian Arctic

- Northern Russia - Baranskaya et al. (2018a)

The compilation of sea level indicators for northern Russia comes from Baranskaya et al. (2018a). Thank you to Alisa V. Baranskaya for sending the references (including translations from Russian) that were missing from the published compilation.

4.4 Southeastern Asia

- Southeastern Asia (SEAMIS) - Mann et al. (2019)

The sea level indicators from southeastern Asia were compiled by Mann et al. (2019). I corrected a number of errors, which are listed in the scratch datasets notes.

4.5 Tropical Corals

- Tropical corals - Hibbert et al. (2016)

Corals from tropical regions were compiled by Hibbert et al. (2016). In this report, I have taken indicators for Huon Peninsula, Vanuatu and French Polynesia from this database. An additional interpretation of the Huon Peninsula data comes from de Gelder et al. (2022).

4.6 Antarctica

- East Antarctica - Ishiwa et al. (2021)
- Antarctica - Briggs and Tarasov (2013)

Currently, I have included two compilations from Antarctica. The compilation by Ishiwa et al. (2021) is focused on East Antarctica and includes MIS 3 data. The other is by Briggs and Tarasov (2013), and includes data from both West and East Antarctica for the Holocene. I also added a couple of sites not included in these compilations, including Hjort et al. (1997) and Braddock et al. (2022).

4.7 Australia

- Australia - (Lewis et al., 2013)
- New South Wales - Sloss et al. (2007)
- Queensland - Larcombe et al. (1995)
- South Australia - Belperio et al. (2002)
- Tasmania - Morrison (2019)

The main compilation of Australia is from Lewis et al. (2013). Thanks goes to Stephen E. Lewis, who kindly sent me the spreadsheets from this compilation and allowed me to include them in this database. This database was actually kind of a “database of databases”, which put together state databases, including New South Wales (Sloss et al., 2007), Queensland (Larcombe et al., 1995) and South Australia (Belperio et al., 2002). Tasmania was not included in the Lewis paper because of a lack of studies. There is a compilation of Tasmania in Morrison (2019), which I have included. In addition, I have included the Great Barrier Reef data from Yokoyama et al. (2018) and Bonaparte Gulf from Yokoyama et al. (2000) and Ishiwa et al. (2019).

4.8 Data locations

Figure 1: Map showing the location of data entered into the database.

5 Summary of results

This is a summary of the results of the modelling. There are a total of six models with which are compared. In addition, these tables give how many sea level indicators, number of marine limiting, number of terrestrial limiting, and number of sea level index points.

The sea level is calculated at the location of each data point. To evaluate how well the calculated curve fits the data point, a score is assigned. This metric was originally used by Gowan et al. (2016). The score is the discrepancy, in number of meters, the calculated sea level falls outside of the constraint plus the error bars. A score is zero if the calculated sea level is consistent with the data point. As an example, if the calculated sea level curve is below a terrestrial limiting point, it is given a score of zero. The sum of the scores for each location for each model are shown in the tables. A warning about the scores is that a lower score does not necessarily mean a better fit, as it will depend on the age distribution of the indicators, and the number of indicators of a specific kind. For example, if there are a lot of marine limiting data points, a calculated curve that is over a hundred meters above those indicators may provide a good score, but it is not necessarily a good fit. As a result, it is a good idea to also look at the plotted curves for visual inspection.

5.1 MIS 1 and 2 (LGM to present)

5.1.1 Antarctica

Table 1: Number of data points and model scores for East Antarctica

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	170	94	55	21	559	812	778	688	607	559	559
Langhovde	51	51	0	0	210	324	293	221	192	210	228
Larsemann Hills	12	2	10	0	53	45	62	80	72	53	45
Ongul Islands	36	7	29	0	48	63	59	49	45	48	50
Rauer Group	32	24	8	0	68	101	111	114	96	68	59
Southern Scott Coast	8	1	0	7	145	187	195	192	172	145	135
Terra Nova Bay	13	4	4	5	7	0	1	2	0	7	13
Vestfold Hills	13	5	0	8	1	62	29	4	5	1	2
Windmill Islands	5	0	4	1	27	30	28	26	25	27	27

Table 2: Number of data points and model scores for West Antarctica

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	93	13	54	26	179	430	409	340	257	179	155
James Ross Is- land	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
King George Is- land	8	0	7	1	10	11	9	8	8	10	11
Marguerite Bay	13	1	12	0	87	130	133	126	108	87	77
Pine Island Bay	63	3	35	25	82	289	267	206	141	82	67

5.1.2 Australia

Table 3: Number of data points and model scores for New South Wales

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	249	139	6	104	228	263	263	253	235	228	233
Lord Howe Is- land	5	0	0	5	20	19	18	17	19	20	20
Nambucca Heads	5	0	0	5	16	17	17	17	16	16	16
Newcastle	12	0	0	12	51	50	51	50	50	51	52
Sydney	32	3	2	27	43	50	50	49	45	43	44
Ulladulla	74	50	0	24	39	50	50	48	42	39	40
Wollongong	121	86	4	31	59	77	77	72	63	59	61

Table 4: Number of data points and model scores for Northern Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	268	39	0	229	564	821	801	726	639	564	558
Bonaparte Gulf	90	19	0	71	211	325	320	291	251	211	206
Bonaparte Gulf SLI Ishiwa2019	84	20	0	64	135	197	192	171	151	135	134
Bonaparte Gulf SLI Yokoyama2000	16	0	0	16	191	263	262	249	224	191	184
Cambridge Gulf	4	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Darwin	5	0	0	5	3	3	3	2	2	3	3
Eastern Timor Sea	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sahul Shelf SLI Ishiwa2019	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sahul Shelf SLI Yokoyama2000	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
South Alligator River	64	0	0	64	24	32	24	13	11	24	31

Table 5: Number of data points and model scores for Queensland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	1078	62	0	1016	4748	4767	4752	4700	4656	4748	4805
Bowen	57	0	0	57	428	429	430	432	433	428	426
Brisbane	7	0	0	7	20	22	22	21	20	20	21
Cairns	322	6	0	316	1722	1625	1631	1641	1658	1722	1748
Cape Melville	69	18	0	51	237	245	241	231	225	237	243
Gladstone	3	0	0	3	5	5	5	5	4	5	5
Hydrographers Passage	281	38	0	243	590	696	694	675	631	590	585
Sunshine Coast	3	0	0	3	14	14	14	13	13	14	14
Townsville	336	0	0	336	1732	1731	1715	1682	1672	1732	1763

Table 6: Number of data points and model scores for South Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	208	80	0	128	511	558	552	519	496	511	528
Franklin Harbour	15	7	0	8	42	45	45	42	40	42	43
Gulf St Vincent	84	32	0	52	197	217	216	207	198	197	202
Port Lincoln	12	2	0	10	37	37	38	38	36	37	37
Redcliff	73	24	0	49	171	193	187	171	163	171	179
Smoky Bay	24	15	0	9	64	66	66	61	59	64	67

Table 7: Number of data points and model scores for Tasmania

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	28	5	7	16	38	48	54	57	49	38	37
Circular Head	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Flinders Island	4	1	0	3	5	6	7	7	6	5	5
Glamorgan-Spring Bay	12	0	0	12	27	34	37	39	34	27	26
Hobart	9	4	4	1	6	8	10	11	9	6	6
King Island	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 8: Number of data points and model scores for Western Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	176	0	0	176	634	676	695	703	671	634	630
Albany	4	0	0	4	7	7	7	8	8	7	7
Broome	2	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2
Bunbury	22	0	0	22	38	41	45	48	43	38	38
Cape Leeuwin	4	0	0	4	6	6	6	7	6	6	6
Esperance	3	0	0	3	7	7	8	8	8	7	7
Exmouth Gulf	17	0	0	17	6	7	9	8	6	6	7
Geraldton	30	0	0	30	69	77	80	79	73	69	69
King Sound	9	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Perth	63	0	0	63	104	115	122	125	115	104	103
Rowley Shoals	10	0	0	10	370	387	388	390	385	370	366
Shark Bay	12	0	0	12	25	27	28	28	26	25	25

5.1.3 Caribbean

Table 9: Number of data points and model scores for Lesser Antilles

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	196	0	0	196	1029	579	566	540	583	1029	1293
Barbados	196	0	0	196	1029	579	566	540	583	1029	1293

5.1.4 East Asia

Table 10: Number of data points and model scores for Ryukyu Islands

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	7	6	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Miyakojima	7	6	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1

Table 11: Number of data points and model scores for Sea of Japan - East Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	13	6	0	7	264	261	264	268	267	264	264
Tsushima-Korea Strait	13	6	0	7	264	261	264	268	267	264	264

5.1.5 Eurasian Arctic

Table 12: Number of data points and model scores for Franz Josef Land

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	170	21	0	149	582	1112	749	435	516	582	567
Proliv Markama	123	15	0	108	398	804	542	299	355	398	388
Zemlya Georga	44	4	0	40	138	228	132	76	110	138	133
Zemlya Zichy	3	2	0	1	46	80	75	60	51	46	46

Table 13: Number of data points and model scores for Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	90	8	19	63	286	486	421	296	278	286	289
Baydaratskaya Bay	2	0	1	1	4	2	3	3	3	4	4
Gulf of Ob	11	0	8	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Kara Sea shelf	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Khalmyer Bay	5	0	3	2	226	216	215	219	224	226	227
Ostrov Sibiryakova	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pechora Sea	5	4	1	0	41	37	29	25	31	41	43
Severny Island North	36	0	0	36	12	140	112	45	20	12	12
Severny Island West	19	1	0	18	2	35	18	0	0	2	1
Vaygach Island	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yuzhny Island	4	1	3	0	0	56	44	4	0	0	1

Table 14: Number of data points and model scores for Southern Barents Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	43	16	1	26	86	99	95	252	162	86	77
Murmansk	21	8	1	12	29	37	44	124	79	29	20
Pechengsky	17	7	0	10	41	53	12	78	70	41	31
Voronya River	5	1	0	4	16	9	39	50	13	16	26

Table 15: Number of data points and model scores for Western Siberia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	125	90	23	12	760	810	824	891	872	760	734
Lena Delta	60	60	0	0	285	299	299	343	350	285	270
New Siberian Islands	8	0	0	8	13	8	6	4	8	13	13
Olenyok Gulf	29	18	11	0	30	28	28	37	41	30	28
Severnaya Zemlya	16	5	11	0	325	350	357	363	346	325	321
West Laptev Sea	10	7	1	2	71	71	76	85	79	71	69
Zhokhov Island	2	0	0	2	36	54	58	59	48	36	33

Table 16: Number of data points and model scores for White Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	177	16	41	120	314	863	953	1024	607	314	273
Belomorsk	8	0	7	1	0	11	16	11	0	0	0
Chupa Bay	15	0	3	12	82	276	372	396	224	82	56
Dvina Gulf	82	4	12	66	47	87	29	24	27	47	60
Eastern Kola Peninsula	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Engozero	8	0	1	7	9	52	87	118	57	9	3
Kandalaksha	8	1	0	7	33	56	40	40	32	33	32
Kholmogorsky	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lesozavodskiy	13	5	0	8	22	86	131	167	89	22	9
Onega Peninsula	9	3	2	4	8	39	18	0	0	8	11
Rugozerskiy Peninsula	15	1	8	6	15	27	4	2	2	15	22
Umba	11	2	0	9	98	229	256	266	176	98	80

5.1.6 Europe

Table 17: Number of data points and model scores for Gulfs Of Riga - Finland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	315	38	174	103	4310	2044	4333	7467	6297	4310	3781
Helsinki	9	0	0	9	151	19	70	210	200	151	137
Hiiumaa	50	14	28	8	437	150	265	644	596	437	392
Lahemaa	7	0	0	7	55	12	30	68	68	55	50
Narva-Luga	58	11	37	10	438	75	436	987	795	438	345
Paldiski	7	0	0	7	80	23	14	97	101	80	73
Parnu	92	3	79	10	1811	1107	2196	3186	2609	1811	1596
Porvoo	10	0	0	10	125	50	53	190	178	125	110
Riga	20	7	13	0	91	58	172	275	193	91	74
Salo	18	0	0	18	343	143	259	497	451	343	311
South Saaremaa	7	0	6	1	156	38	137	239	209	156	142
St Petersburg	1	0	0	1	4	10	22	29	18	4	1
Tallinn	20	0	8	12	382	247	398	601	516	382	345
Virolahti	4	0	0	4	89	38	96	155	130	89	79
Vyborgsky District	6	0	0	6	110	54	129	202	167	110	94
West Gulf Of Riga	6	3	3	0	38	20	56	87	66	38	32

Table 18: Number of data points and model scores for North Baltic

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	76	0	2	74	860	940	816	1377	1183	860	800
Aland	3	0	0	3	28	30	4	40	42	28	23
Alvsbyn	6	0	2	4	37	49	128	187	108	37	25
Angermanland	14	0	0	14	106	318	137	44	66	106	136
Central Finland	1	0	0	1	20	17	1	8	2	20	25
Gastrikland	16	0	0	16	57	167	97	184	134	57	45
Gunnarsbyn	8	0	0	8	134	98	128	246	203	134	113
Oulu	2	0	0	2	28	7	32	61	49	28	22
Satakunta	1	0	0	1	21	3	8	30	28	21	18
South Lapland	4	0	0	4	29	75	50	47	40	29	27
South Os- trobothnia	3	0	0	3	58	15	36	93	84	58	50
Turku	18	0	0	18	342	161	195	437	427	342	316

Table 19: Number of data points and model scores for North Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	417	20	59	338	757	501	547	673	769	757	738
Belgium	22	0	0	22	65	31	45	57	73	65	60
Bremerhaven	51	0	0	51	41	57	38	30	30	41	45
Central Nether- lands	27	0	0	27	105	76	78	69	95	105	105
Dogger Bank	1	0	0	1	16	11	13	17	17	16	16
Elbe	23	0	0	23	6	7	4	16	12	6	4
German Bight	13	0	0	13	49	25	42	80	62	49	46
Ho Bugt	20	0	0	20	26	2	2	31	32	26	25
Langeoog	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Limfjord	27	20	7	0	23	37	38	77	49	23	18
Netherlands	5	0	0	5	12	12	11	7	10	12	13
Wadden Sea											
Norderney	56	0	0	56	33	43	31	21	23	33	36
Oyster Ground	2	0	0	2	3	0	2	5	3	3	3
Rotterdam	165	0	52	113	368	195	237	253	354	368	357
Southern Bight	4	0	0	4	10	5	6	10	9	10	10

Table 20: Number of data points and model scores for Skagerrak - Kattegat

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	339	200	107	32	346	793	487	665	476	346	343
Asa	5	0	0	5	64	79	86	127	98	64	55
Bohuslan	5	0	0	5	25	42	38	70	50	25	19
Goteborg	2	0	0	2	33	23	46	64	49	33	29
Halmstad	1	0	0	1	16	13	23	31	24	16	13
Kattegat	26	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kieler Bucht	3	3	0	0	19	25	9	0	7	19	22
Laesoe	3	2	0	1	1	9	1	1	1	1	1
Lillebaelt	25	14	11	0	67	104	47	17	41	67	75
Samsø Belt	66	47	8	11	9	185	50	39	27	9	6
Storebaelt	65	25	38	2	46	77	50	107	59	46	53
Copenhagen	78	28	49	1	35	126	99	169	90	35	26
Treoa Moelle- bugt	4	4	0	0	0	30	11	0	0	0	0
Vendsyssel Thy	56	51	1	4	31	80	27	40	30	31	44

Table 21: Number of data points and model scores for South Baltic

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	489	112	206	171	1586	1998	1805	2165	1781	1586	1578
Achterwasser	26	0	6	20	76	126	84	26	45	76	85
Arkona Basin East	30	29	0	1	205	137	37	17	92	205	233
Arkona Basin West	24	12	11	1	52	63	35	20	33	52	57
Baltic South	2	2	0	0	7	4	0	0	0	7	10
Baltic South- west	7	6	0	1	6	16	16	15	4	6	11
Blekinge	38	2	10	26	117	241	228	402	284	117	75
Curonian Spit	1	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
Fakse Bugt	11	7	4	0	132	42	23	27	85	132	143
Havang	54	1	43	10	84	104	305	639	301	84	52
Lithuania	43	25	18	0	142	209	313	391	268	142	116
Lubeck	69	18	36	15	290	279	195	136	211	290	309
Ostergotland	6	0	0	6	29	51	57	80	59	29	21
Rugen	53	5	8	40	211	386	243	52	111	211	236
Salt Meadows	43	0	1	42	110	216	141	32	61	110	123
Sodermanland	9	0	0	9	44	93	51	85	72	44	39
South Vistula	49	2	47	0	27	11	10	99	63	27	24
Ustka	2	0	2	0	0	0	1	8	0	0	0
Ventspils	5	1	4	0	48	17	65	109	82	48	39
West Gulf Of Gdansk	17	1	16	0	6	0	1	27	10	6	5

5.1.7 Greenland

Table 22: Number of data points and model scores for Northeast Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	534	443	29	62	6881	5068	6106	6956	6380	6881	7440
Cape Morris Jesup	73	67	6	0	841	330	485	685	696	841	942
Danmarks Fjord	30	27	0	3	733	531	610	688	680	733	778
Frederick E Hyde Fjord	16	14	1	1	259	115	150	207	218	259	286
Germania Land	14	14	0	0	255	143	189	234	228	255	279
Hochstetter Forland	20	12	8	0	228	150	194	224	208	228	245
Hold With Hope	17	16	0	1	84	41	71	100	73	84	102
Independence Fjord	12	11	1	0	69	26	36	57	57	69	82
JP Koch Fjord	2	2	0	0	33	20	22	27	28	33	36
Jameson Land	17	12	5	0	57	81	106	105	63	57	66
Kap Clarence Wyckoff	32	29	0	3	795	570	657	745	734	795	845
Kempes Fjord	10	10	0	0	31	23	29	35	29	31	34
Kong Oscars Fjord	53	50	0	3	183	163	213	240	180	183	203
Nansen land	6	6	0	0	90	23	33	60	68	90	103
Nioghalvfjerdingsfjorden	17	17	0	0	220	137	165	201	198	220	241
Prinsesse Ingeborg Halvøe	67	63	1	3	1102	847	955	1048	1027	1102	1167
Renland	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	1
Schuchert Dal	97	63	0	34	1631	1670	1940	1998	1637	1631	1734
Traill Oe	19	18	0	1	94	85	106	116	91	94	103
Young Sound	27	8	6	13	176	113	145	182	165	176	193

Table 23: Number of data points and model scores for Northwest Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	150	81	6	63	2035	962	999	1181	1496	2035	2258
Bessel Fjord	36	3	0	33	373	503	527	507	461	373	345
Cass Fjord	16	15	1	0	122	117	114	113	115	122	129
Hall Land	66	37	0	29	528	175	190	248	329	528	630
Inglefield Fjord	10	6	4	0	191	69	56	60	109	191	220
Nordvestoe	3	3	0	0	93	0	0	0	26	93	115
Thule	11	10	0	1	668	87	97	230	421	668	747
Tuttulissuaq	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warming Land	4	4	0	0	51	11	15	23	32	51	60
Wulff land	3	3	0	0	9	0	0	0	3	9	12

Table 24: Number of data points and model scores for Southeast Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	6	0	2	4	20	33	43	44	23	20	25
Ammassalik	6	0	2	4	20	33	43	44	23	20	25

Table 25: Number of data points and model scores for Southwest Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	320	114	59	147	11283	7434	7758	8313	9001	11283	12255
Akullit	24	10	1	13	719	351	364	420	502	719	816
Alluttoq Island	10	0	2	8	284	164	169	189	216	284	312
Egalussuit	5	5	0	0	252	91	99	128	169	252	281
Tasiat											
Ikertoq Fjord	7	5	0	2	416	254	261	286	326	416	450
Ilulissat	12	2	3	7	201	116	118	129	147	201	225
Itilleq	11	2	0	9	265	155	160	174	201	265	291
Kangerluk	9	0	0	9	447	308	311	331	367	447	479
Kangerlussuaq	34	20	4	10	935	535	552	603	687	935	1046
Kannala	33	3	3	27	1125	611	623	693	816	1125	1248
Kapisillit	26	8	17	1	235	98	106	121	142	235	273
Maniitsoq	5	5	0	0	251	120	127	148	181	251	277
Nanortalik	24	0	0	24	917	880	939	941	869	917	959
Nuuk	44	25	19	0	1096	522	564	651	778	1096	1219
Paamiut	10	0	1	9	541	421	438	455	471	541	571
Qaqortoq	30	11	0	19	1410	1299	1371	1379	1306	1410	1481
Qeqertarsuatsiaat	11	11	0	0	730	480	503	541	592	730	784
Sisimiut	12	3	0	9	1215	878	894	950	1037	1215	1279
Tasiussarsuaq	13	4	9	0	244	151	159	174	194	244	264

5.1.8 North America Arctic

Table 26: Number of data points and model scores for Hudson Bay

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	243	114	68	61	2508	1744	2851	4744	4250	2508	2068
Churchill	23	10	7	6	122	63	160	386	339	122	58
East James Bay	36	20	9	7	589	320	565	982	918	589	474
Inukjuak	21	11	2	8	72	5	28	111	118	72	59
Ivujivik	21	14	2	5	40	28	41	105	61	40	174
Kivalliq	31	21	5	5	226	59	159	322	324	226	185
Umiujaq	94	34	33	27	1358	1161	1724	2488	2211	1358	1066
West James Bay	17	4	10	3	101	108	174	350	279	101	52

Table 27: Number of data points and model scores for Hudson Strait

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	86	65	18	3	943	119	262	467	410	943	1354
Kangiqtujuaq	14	13	1	0	138	0	0	5	5	138	222
Southern	7	2	2	3	106	74	136	215	192	106	76
Ungava Bay											
Sugluk	40	30	10	0	572	2	27	96	82	572	917
Western Un-gava Bay	25	20	5	0	127	43	99	151	131	127	139

5.1.9 North America Atlantic

Table 28: Number of data points and model scores for Eastern United States

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	357	138	38	181	919	490	774	970	859	919	1000
Eastern Shore	28	7	6	15	72	21	47	68	64	72	78
Inner Chesapeake	106	99	0	7	176	172	200	168	143	176	199
Inner Delaware	38	2	8	28	104	31	71	86	75	104	122
Northern North Carolina	60	23	6	31	225	150	215	266	231	225	237
Northern South Carolina	18	0	8	10	48	9	31	66	59	48	47
Outer Delaware	60	5	5	50	172	85	137	153	136	172	197
Southern North Carolina	24	2	3	19	40	4	19	47	45	40	41
Southern South Carolina	23	0	2	21	82	18	54	116	106	82	79

Table 29: Number of data points and model scores for Labrador

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	61	16	45	0	230	94	140	240	188	230	290
Hamilton Inlet	15	3	12	0	0	0	0	10	3	0	8
Lake Melville	12	4	8	0	5	0	4	15	14	5	1
Nain	16	2	14	0	8	94	135	192	134	8	0
Torngat	18	7	11	0	217	0	1	23	37	217	281

Table 30: Number of data points and model scores for Maritimes

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	533	121	122	290	1654	2679	2954	4488	3750	1654	1226
Anticosti Island	24	13	3	8	252	307	396	525	437	252	189
Cape Breton	16	4	7	5	9	18	5	37	51	9	2
Chaleur Bay	15	10	5	0	5	0	0	18	19	5	3
Cumberland	112	6	15	91	54	296	237	64	26	54	110
Forestville	59	18	7	34	294	306	357	571	533	294	215
Halifax	48	15	4	29	11	108	53	15	15	11	30
Magdalen Islands	22	2	11	9	8	4	27	63	53	8	3
Passamaquoddy Bay	28	8	11	9	23	119	159	146	74	23	22
Prince Edward Island	31	9	6	16	27	130	116	97	82	27	29
Quebec City	69	18	28	23	148	421	314	900	746	148	74
Rimouski	90	17	15	58	818	946	1272	2037	1701	818	539
Sable Island	10	1	6	3	3	20	13	12	9	3	6
Shelburne	9	0	4	5	2	4	5	3	4	2	4

Table 31: Number of data points and model scores for Newfoundland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgA	PM ₁ A _h ehgC	PM ₁ A _h ehgG	PM ₁ A _h ehgk	PM ₁ A _h ehgr	PM ₁ A _h ehgK
Total	160	53	61	46	372	425	508	567	490	372	388
Avalon Peninsula	13	3	5	5	4	3	4	4	3	4	5
Bay Of Islands	16	5	3	8	18	50	98	147	104	18	4
Great Northern Peninsula	56	16	23	17	208	181	120	42	76	208	280
Notre Dame Bay	29	12	13	4	20	40	59	67	47	20	17
Port Aux Basques	46	17	17	12	122	151	227	307	260	122	82

Table 32: Number of data points and model scores for Northeastern United States

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	479	51	117	311	1273	1799	1588	829	647	1273	1650
Connecticut	95	0	41	54	85	64	82	64	54	85	103
Eastern Maine	49	0	4	45	104	268	228	58	20	104	155
Long Island	25	0	6	19	129	166	156	100	89	129	149
New Jersey	62	6	11	45	200	141	180	169	150	200	230
New York	76	6	19	51	260	222	276	186	146	260	323
Northern Mas- sachusetts	43	3	16	24	70	89	91	50	39	70	86
Southern Maine	86	24	6	56	331	712	461	156	106	331	485
Southern Mas- sachusetts	43	12	14	17	94	137	114	46	43	94	119

5.1.10 Pacific Islands

Table 33: Number of data points and model scores for French Polynesia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	191	0	0	191	157	196	195	194	178	157	155
Mururoa	12	0	0	12	119	142	140	136	126	119	118
Tahiti	179	0	0	179	38	54	55	58	52	38	37

Table 34: Number of data points and model scores for Melansia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	82	11	0	71	19	20	19	18	19	19	19
Vanuatu	82	11	0	71	19	20	19	18	19	19	19

5.1.11 Proxy Based Sea Level

Table 35: Number of data points and model scores for Red Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	165	0	0	165	29	59	63	59	45	29	26
Bab-el-Mandeb proxy	165	0	0	165	29	59	63	59	45	29	26

5.1.12 South Asia

Table 36: Number of data points and model scores for Bay of Bengal

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	5	4	0	1	5	16	15	12	9	5	5
Ganges Delta	5	4	0	1	5	16	15	12	9	5	5

5.1.13 Southeast Asia

Table 37: Number of data points and model scores for Java Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	72	18	2	52	319	352	336	314	295	319	333
Belitung Island	25	0	0	25	114	145	131	112	103	114	120
Central Java	6	0	0	6	31	34	33	31	29	31	32
South Sulawesi	41	18	2	21	174	173	172	171	163	174	181

Table 38: Number of data points and model scores for Papua New Guinea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	58	35	0	23	14	3	3	4	7	14	16
Huon Peninsula	58	35	0	23	14	3	3	4	7	14	16

Table 39: Number of data points and model scores for South China Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	2	0	2	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	0
Xisha Islands	2	0	2	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	0

Table 40: Number of data points and model scores for Sundaland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	375	88	104	183	606	868	801	690	604	606	630
Ca Na	18	7	8	3	37	36	34	32	31	37	39
Chao Phraya	33	5	9	19	89	96	80	65	66	89	98
East Malay Peninsula	4	3	1	0	7	10	8	6	5	7	8
Mekong Delta	71	2	24	45	49	61	59	65	58	49	53
Phuket	40	20	13	7	41	47	42	36	33	41	45
Southeast Malay Peninsula	13	12	0	1	36	48	43	35	32	36	38
Strait Of Malacca	137	29	45	63	164	211	184	154	144	164	174
Sunda Shelf	49	7	3	39	163	325	316	266	210	163	156
Thale Noi	3	0	1	2	6	7	6	4	4	6	7
Vietnam Shelf	5	1	0	4	12	24	26	25	19	12	10
West Malay Peninsula	2	2	0	0	2	3	3	2	2	2	2

5.2 MIS 3 and 4

5.2.1 Antarctica

Table 41: Number of data points and model scores for East Antarctica

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	68	62	6	0	2723	2488	2468	2499	2596	2723	2749
Langhovde	19	19	0	0	813	756	748	752	777	813	822
Larsemann Hills	5	1	4	0	50	34	36	40	45	50	50
Ongul Islands	35	35	0	0	1683	1584	1569	1576	1619	1683	1697
Rauer Group	9	7	2	0	177	114	115	131	155	177	180

5.2.2 Australia

Table 42: Number of data points and model scores for Northern Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	11	3	0	8	217	254	251	244	233	217	214
Bonaparte Gulf	4	1	0	3	81	95	94	91	87	81	80
Bonaparte Gulf SLI Ishiwa2019	4	2	0	2	55	64	63	62	59	55	54
Bonaparte Gulf SLI Yokoyama2000	3	0	0	3	81	95	94	91	87	81	80

Table 43: Number of data points and model scores for Queensland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	74	22	0	52	744	922	916	882	822	744	723
Cairns	45	11	0	34	646	789	784	756	709	646	628
Hydrographers Passage	28	11	0	17	82	120	119	112	99	82	78
Townsville	1	0	0	1	16	13	13	14	14	16	17

5.2.3 Caribbean

Table 44: Number of data points and model scores for Lesser Antilles

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	8	0	0	8	174	147	148	152	157	174	180
Barbados	8	0	0	8	174	147	148	152	157	174	180

5.2.4 East Asia

Table 45: Number of data points and model scores for Ryukyu Islands

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	76	70	0	6	8	23	20	16	11	8	9
Kikaijima 1.9 mm	38	35	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Kikaijima 2.1 mm	38	35	0	3	8	22	20	16	11	8	9

Table 46: Number of data points and model scores for Sea of Japan - East Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	4	1	1	2	77	100	98	92	83	77	77
Tsushima-Korea Strait	4	1	1	2	77	100	98	92	83	77	77

Table 47: Number of data points and model scores for Yellow Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	11	11	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	3
South Bohai Sea	4	4	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	3
Yellow Sea	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

5.2.5 Greenland

Table 48: Number of data points and model scores for Northeast Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	9	9	0	0	201	228	239	248	224	201	194
Cape Morris Jessup	4	4	0	0	82	98	104	108	95	82	79
Kap Clarence Wyckoff	4	4	0	0	78	90	93	96	87	78	75
Nansen land	1	1	0	0	41	40	42	44	42	41	40

5.2.6 North America Atlantic

Table 49: Number of data points and model scores for Eastern United States

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	23	5	15	3	104	203	192	154	122	104	98
Eastern Shore	6	1	5	0	13	30	27	19	15	13	11
Northern North Carolina	14	4	7	3	91	173	165	135	107	91	87
Southern North Carolina	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

5.2.7 Pacific Islands

Table 50: Number of data points and model scores for French Polynesia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	19	0	0	19	224	246	245	241	232	224	223
Mururoa	2	0	0	2	0	4	4	3	1	0	0
Tahiti	17	0	0	17	224	242	241	238	231	224	223

Table 51: Number of data points and model scores for Melansia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	6	0	0	6	25	24	24	25	25	25	24
Vanuatu	6	0	0	6	25	24	24	25	25	25	24

5.2.8 Proxy Based Sea Level

Table 52: Number of data points and model scores for Java Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	15	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Karimata Strait proxy	15	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 53: Number of data points and model scores for Red Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	318	0	0	318	5175	6770	6653	6190	5647	5175	5152
Bab-el-Mandeb proxy	318	0	0	318	5175	6770	6653	6190	5647	5175	5152

5.2.9 South Asia

Table 54: Number of data points and model scores for Bay of Bengal

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	2	1	0	1	27	36	35	33	30	27	26
Ganges Delta	2	1	0	1	27	36	35	33	30	27	26

5.2.10 Southeast Asia

Table 55: Number of data points and model scores for Papua New Guinea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	52	0	0	52	115	118	119	118	117	115	113
Huon Peninsula	40	0	0	40	55	54	55	55	55	55	54
Huon Peninsula de Gelder	12	0	0	12	60	64	64	63	62	60	59

Table 56: Number of data points and model scores for South China Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	1	0	1	0	19	27	26	24	21	19	18
Xisha Islands	1	0	1	0	19	27	26	24	21	19	18

Table 57: Number of data points and model scores for Sundaland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgA	PM_1_A_h ehgC	PM_1_A_h ehgG	PM_1_A_h ehgk	PM_1_A_h ehgr	PM_1_A_h ehgK
Total	33	14	17	2	283	319	315	302	291	283	281
Berhala Strait	2	0	1	1	16	13	13	14	14	16	16
Chao Phraya	3	3	0	0	77	58	59	63	69	77	79
Mekong Delta	1	1	0	0	20	14	15	16	18	20	21
Strait Of Malacca	11	2	9	0	10	20	19	16	13	10	9
Sunda Shelf	15	7	7	1	160	214	209	193	177	160	156
Vietnam Shelf	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6 MIS 1 and 2 (LGM to present) – Sea level Indicators and Proxies

The Holocene (roughly equivalent to MIS 1) spans from 11.65 kyr before present to present. MIS 2 encompasses the Last Glacial Maximum (27-19 kyr BP) and the deglacial period that goes until the end of the Younger Dryas. In general, paleo sea level proxies are abundant in the Holocene, when sea level was within 30 m of present, but are uncommon before that. The lack of proxies older than the Holocene is in a large part due to their inaccessibility (in water too deep for typical coring methods). In most cases, MIS 2 aged sea level proxies are from drowned coral reefs in tropical areas, or in relatively broad continental shelves.

6.1 Antarctica

6.1.1 East Antarctica

Figure 2: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Langhovde. References: Hayashi and Yoshida (1994); Hirakawa and Sawagaki (1998); Igarashi et al. (1995a,b); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Maemoku et al. (1997); Miura et al. (1998); Verleyen et al. (2017).

Figure 3: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Larsemann Hills. References: Hodgson et al. (2009); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Verleyen et al. (2005).

Figure 4: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Ongul Islands. References: Hirakawa and Sawagaki (1998); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Miura et al. (1998); Verleyen et al. (2017).

Figure 5: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Rauer Group. References: Berg et al. (2010a,b, 2016); Hodgson et al. (2016); Ishiwa et al. (2021).

Figure 6: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Southern Scott Coast. References: Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Hall et al. (2004).

Figure 7: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Terra Nova Bay. References: Baroni and Hall (2004); Briggs and Tarasov (2013).

Figure 8: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Vestfold Hills. References: Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Zhang and Peterson (1984); Zwartz et al. (1998).

Figure 9: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Windmill Islands. References: Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Goodwin (1993); Goodwin and Zweck (2000).

6.1.2 West Antarctica

Figure 10: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: James Ross Island. References: Hjort et al. (1997).

Figure 11: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: King George Island. References: Barsch and Mäusbacher (1986); Bentley et al. (2005); Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Del Valle et al. (2002); Martinez-Macchiavello et al. (1996); Schmidt et al. (1990).

Figure 12: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: Marguerite Bay. References: Bentley et al. (2005); Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Emslie and McDaniel (2002); Wasell and Håkansson (1992).

Figure 13: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: Pine Island Bay. References: Braddock et al. (2022); Johnson et al. (2008); Lindow et al. (2014).

6.2 Australia

6.2.1 New South Wales

Figure 14: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Lord Howe Island. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Woodroffe et al. (2010).

Figure 15: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Nambucca Heads. References: Baker et al. (2001a,b); Flood and Frankel (1989); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Sloss et al. (2007).

Figure 16: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Newcastle. References: Baker et al. (2001a,b); Gillespie and Temple (1976); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Sloss et al. (2007); Thom and Chappell (1975); Thom and Roy (1983).

Figure 17: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Sydney. References: Baker et al. (2001a); Baker and Haworth (2000, 1997); Baker et al. (2001b); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Roy and Crawford (1981); Sloss et al. (2007); Thom and Chappell (1975); Thom and Roy (1983); Thom et al. (1969).

Figure 18: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Ulladulla. References: Baker et al. (2001b); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Sloss et al. (2004); Sloss (2005); Sloss et al. (2006, 2007, 2019); Thom and Chappell (1975).

Figure 19: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Wollongong. References: Bryant et al. (1992); Carne (1981); Jones et al. (1979); Jones (1990); Lewis et al. (2013); Murray-Wallace et al. (2000); Panayotou (2004); Sloss et al. (2004); Sloss (2005); Sloss et al. (2006, 2007); Umitsu et al. (2001); Young et al. (1993).

6.2.2 Northern Australia

Figure 20: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf. References: Hubbs and Bien (1967); Ishiwa et al. (2019); Lewis et al. (2013); Nicholas et al. (2014); van Andel et al. (1967); Yokoyama et al. (2000).

Figure 21: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Ishiwa *et al.* 2019 interpretation). References: Ishiwa *et al.* (2019); Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 22: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Yokoyama *et al.* 2000 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 23: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Cambridge Gulf. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Thom et al. (1975).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 24: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Darwin. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Nott (1996).

Figure 25: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Eastern Timor Sea. References: Nicholas et al. (2014).

Figure 26: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Sahul Shelf (Ishiwa *et al.* 2019 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
 - Index point ($>10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 27: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Sahul Shelf (Yokoyama *et al.* 2000 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 28: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: South Alligator River. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Woodroffe et al. (1986, 1985, 1987).

6.2.3 Queensland

Figure 29: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Bowen. References: Belperio (1978, 1979); Blake (1994); Chappell et al. (1983); Harris et al. (1990); Heap et al. (2002); Hopley (1980, 1983); Hopley et al. (1978, 1983); Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2013); Thom et al. (1969); Way (1987).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 30: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Brisbane. References: Flood (1983); Hekel et al. (1979); Hofmann (1980); Jones et al. (1978); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 31: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Cairns. References: Bird (1971); Chappell et al. (1983); Crowley et al. (1990); Gagan (1990); Gagan et al. (1994); Grant-Taylor and Rafter (1963); Johnson and Carter (1987); Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2013); Partain and Hopley (1989); Yokoyama et al. (2018); Zwartz (1995).

Figure 32: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Cape Melville. References: Chappell et al. (1983); Higley (2000); Lewis et al. (2013); Salama (1991); Zwartz (1995).

Figure 33: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Gladstone. References: Flood (1983); Lewis et al. (2013); Yokoyama et al. (2006).

Figure 34: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Hydrographers Passage. References: Yokoyama et al. (2018).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 35: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Sunshine Coast. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Thom et al. (1969); Wood (1972).

Figure 36: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Townsville. References: Beaman et al. (1994); Belperio (1978, 1979); Carter et al. (1993); Chappell et al. (1983); Gill and Hopley (1972); Grindrod and Rhodes (1984); Harris et al. (1990); Higley (2000); Hopley (1980, 1983); Hopley et al. (1983); Johnson et al. (1984); Johnson and Risk (1987); Larcombe and Carter (1998); Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2008, 2013, 2015); Ohlenbusch (1991); Pye and Rhodes (1985); Spenceley (1980); Tye (1992); Walbran (1991); Woodroffe (2009); Yu and Zhao (2010); Zwartz (1995).

6.2.4 South Australia

Figure 37: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Franklin Harbour. References: Belperio et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Short et al. (1986).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehg

Figure 38: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Gulf St Vincent. References: Belperio (1993); Belperio et al. (1983, 2002); Cann et al. (1988, 1993); Lewis et al. (2013); Murray-Wallace et al. (1993).

Figure 39: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Port Lincoln. References: Belperio et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Short et al. (1986).

Figure 40: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Redcliff. References: Belperio et al. (1984, 2002); Harvey et al. (1999); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 41: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Smoky Bay. References: Belperio et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Murray-Wallace et al. (1993); Short et al. (1986).

6.2.5 Tasmania

Figure 42: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Circular Head. References: Morrison (2019); Murray-Wallace and Goede (1995).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 43: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Flinders Island. References: Morrison (2019); Murray-Wallace and Goede (1995).

Figure 44: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Glamorgan-Spring Bay. References: Gehrels et al. (2012); Morrison (2019).

Figure 45: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Hobart. References: Clark et al. (2011); Morrison (2019).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 46: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: King Island. References: Morrison (2019); Murray-Wallace and Goede (1995).

6.2.6 Western Australia

Figure 47: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Albany. References: Baker et al. (2005); Lewis et al. (2013).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 48: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Broome. References: Hearty et al. (2006); Lessa and Masselink (2006); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 49: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Bunbury. References: Baker et al. (2005); Buckley and Valdes-Pages (1981); Lewis et al. (2013); Searle and Logan (1978); Semeniuk (1985, 1996).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 50: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Cape Leeuwin. References: Baker et al. (2005); Lewis et al. (2013); Sas (1974).

Figure 51: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Esperance. References: Baker et al. (2005); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 52: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Exmouth Gulf. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Logan et al. (1970); Twigg and Collins (2010).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 53: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Geraldton. References: Collins et al. (2006); Eisenhauer et al. (1993); Lewis et al. (2013); Veeh and France (1988); Wyrwoll (1977).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 54: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: King Sound. References: Jennings (1975); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 55: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Perth. References: Baker et al. (2001b, 2005); Brown et al. (1980); Deevey et al. (1959); Gillespie and Temple (1976); Kendrick (1977); Kigoshi et al. (1973); Lewis et al. (2013); Playford (1988); Searle and Woods (1986); Searle et al. (1988); Tamers et al. (1964).

Figure 56: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Rowley Shoals. References: James et al. (2004); Lewis et al. (2013).

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 57: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Shark Bay. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Logan et al. (1970); Noakes and Brandau (1971); Noakes et al. (1967, 1968); Read (1974).

6.3 Caribbean

6.3.1 Lesser Antilles

Figure 58: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Lesser Antilles, location: Barbados. References: Abdul et al. (2016); Fairbanks (1988); Fairbanks et al. (2005); Mortlock et al. (2005, 2016); Peltier and Fairbanks (2006).

6.4 East Asia

6.4.1 Ryukyu Islands

Figure 59: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Ryukyu Islands, location: Miyakojima. References: Sasaki et al. (2006).

6.4.2 Sea of Japan - East Sea

Figure 60: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sea of Japan - East Sea, location: Tsushima-Korea Strait. References: Park et al. (2000).

6.5 Eurasian Arctic

6.5.1 Franz Josef Land

Figure 61: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Franz Josef Land, location: Proliv Markama. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009); Forman and Polyak (1997); Forman et al. (1996, 2004); Grosswald (1963); Grosswald et al. (1973); Gusev et al. (2013b); Kovaleva (1974); Lubinski (1998); Weihe (1996).

Figure 62: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Franz Josef Land, location: Zemlya Georga. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009); Dibner (1965); Forman et al. (1996, 2004); Glazovskiy et al. (1992); Grosswald et al. (1973); Kovaleva (1974).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Figure 63: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Franz Josef Land, location: Zemlya Zichy. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009).

6.5.2 Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya

Figure 64: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Baydaratskaya Bay. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Belova (2012); Romanenko et al. (2007).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Figure 65: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Gulf of Ob. References: Astakhov and Nazarov (2010); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Makeev (1988); Makeev et al. (1988).

Figure 66: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Kara Sea shelf. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Levitan et al. (2007); Polyakova and Stein (2004).

Figure 67: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Khalmyer Bay. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a,b); Grigorieva (1987).

Figure 68: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Ostrov Sibiryakova. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Gusev et al. (2013a).

Figure 69: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Pechora Sea. References: Astakhov et al. (2007); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Krapivner (2006); Polyak et al. (2000); Zhuravlev et al. (2013).

Figure 70: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Severny Island North. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Forman et al. (1999, 2004); Gawronski and Zeeberg (1997); Zeeberg et al. (2001).

Figure 71: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Severny Island West. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009); Forman et al. (1999, 2004); Zeeberg et al. (2001).

Figure 72: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Vaygach Island. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Forman et al. (2004); Zeeberg et al. (2001).

Figure 73: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Yuzhny Island. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2006); Mangerud et al. (2008); Zhuravlev et al. (2013).

6.5.3 Southern Barents Sea

Figure 74: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southern Barents Sea, location: Murmansk. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Corner et al. (2001); Gurevich and Liyva (1975); Gurina (1971); Mityaev M. V. (2008); Tanner (1907).

Figure 75: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southern Barents Sea, location: Pechengsky. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Corner et al. (1999); Koshechkin (1979).

Figure 76: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southern Barents Sea, location: Voronya River. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Snyder et al. (1997).

6.5.4 Western Siberia

Figure 77: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Lena Delta. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Makarov (2009).

Figure 78: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: New Siberian Islands. References: Anisimov et al. (2009a); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyaynov et al. (2013); Polyakova et al. (2005).

Figure 79: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Olenyok Gulf. References: Andreev et al. (2004); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2013); Makarov (2009).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Figure 80: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Severnaya Zemlya. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov and Makeev (1995); Raab et al. (2003).

Figure 81: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: West Laptev Sea. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bauch et al. (1999); Bolshiyarov et al. (2013); Winterfeld et al. (2011).

Figure 82: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Zhokhov Island. References: Anisimov et al. (2009b); Baranskaya et al. (2018a).

6.5.5 White Sea

Figure 83: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Belomorsk. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Devyatova and Liyva (1971); Koshechkin (1979); Lunkka et al. (2012).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 84: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Chupa Bay. References: Baranskaya and Romanenko (2015); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2015).

Figure 85: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Dvina Gulf. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Koshechkin (1979); Zaretskaya et al. (2011).

Figure 86: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Eastern Kola Peninsula. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Koshechkin (1979).

Figure 87: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Engozero. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2013b).

Figure 88: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Kandalaksha. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka and Korsakova (2010); Koshechkin (1979).

Figure 89: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Kholmogorsky. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Larsen et al. (2006).

Figure 90: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Lesozavodskiy. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2005); Koshechkin et al. (1973).

Figure 91: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Onega Peninsula. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Boyarskaya et al. (1986); Koshechkin et al. (1973); Repkina et al. (in review).

Figure 92: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Rugozerskiy Peninsula. References: Baranskaya (2015); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Repkina and Romanenko (2016); Romanenko and Shilova (2012); Zaretskaya et al. (2013).

Figure 93: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Umba. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2013a); Koshechkin (1979).

6.6 Europe

6.6.1 Gulfs Of Riga - Finland

Figure 94: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Helsinki. References: Alhonen (1972); Alhonen et al. (1978); Hyvärinen (1979, 1982, 1984); Rosentau et al. (2021); Seppä et al. (2000).

Figure 95: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Hiiumaa. References: Kriiska (2002); Kriiska and Lõugas (1999); Kriiska et al. (2005); Königsson et al. (1998); Liiva et al. (1966); Rosentau et al. (2020, 2021); Sarv (1981); Vassiljev et al. (2015).

Figure 96: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Lahemaa. References: Grudzinska et al. (2013); Muru et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021); Saarse et al. (2009).

Figure 97: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Narva-Luga. References: Jaanits and Liiva (1973); Kessel (1963); Kriiska (1995, 1996); Lepland et al. (1996); Rosentau et al. (2013, 2021); Saarse et al. (2003); Sandgren et al. (2004).

Figure 98: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Paldiski. References: Grudzinska et al. (2013); Muru et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 99: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Parnu. References: H. (1975); Habicht et al. (2017); Haila and Raukas (1992); Hyvärinen et al. (1992); Ilves et al. (1974); Jaanits and Jaanits (1978); Jonuks (2013, 2016); Kessel and Punning (1969a,b, 1974); Kriiska (2001); Kriiska and Lõugas (2009); Kriiska et al. (2002); Nirgi et al. (2020); Orru et al. (1992); Poska and Veski (1999); Punning et al. (1971, 1977); Raukas et al. (1995, 1999); Rosentau et al. (2011, 2021); Saarse et al. (2003); Veski (1998); Veski et al. (2005).

Figure 100: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Porvoo. References: Donner and Eronen (1981); Eronen (1974); Haila et al. (1991); Jungner and Sonninen (1983); Miettinen et al. (1999); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 101: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Riga. References: Eberhards (2008); Grudzinska (2015); Grudzinska et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 102: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Salo. References: Eronen (1974); Eronen et al. (1993, 2001); Glückert (1976, 1978b); Leino (1973); Ristaniemi and Glückert (1988); Rosentau et al. (2021); Tolonen and Tolonen (1988).

Figure 103: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: South Saaremaa. References: Reintam et al. (2008); Rosentau et al. (2021); Saarse et al. (2009).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 104: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: St Petersburg. References: Morozov (2014); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 105: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Tallinn. References: Grudzinska et al. (2014); Heinsalu (2000); Lõugas and Tomek (2013); Muru et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021); Sarse et al. (2006, 2009); Veski (1998).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 106: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Virolahti. References: Miettinen (2002); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 107: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Vyborgsky District. References: Miettinen et al. (2007); Morozov (2014); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 108: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: West Gulf Of Riga. References: Eberhards (2006); Grudzinska (2011); Pujāte (2015); Punning et al. (1973); Rosentau et al. (2021); Veinbergs (1996).

6.6.2 North Baltic

Figure 109: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Åland. References: Glückert (1978a); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 110: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Alvsbyn. References: Lindén et al. (2006); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 111: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Angermanland. References: Berglund (2004, 2008); Rosentau et al. (2021); Wallin (1994).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 112: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Central Finland. References: Ristaniemi (1987); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 113: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Gasterikland. References: Berglund (2005, 2010, 2012); Hedenström and Risberg (2003); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 114: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Gunnarsbyn. References: Lindén et al. (2006); Rosentau et al. (2021).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 115: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Oulu. References: Eronen (1974); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 116: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Satakunta. References: Rosentau et al. (2021); Salomaa (1982).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 117: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: South Lapland. References: Eronen (1974); Rosentau et al. (2021); Saarnisto (1981).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 118: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: South Ostrobothnia. References: Eronen (1974); Glückert et al. (1993); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 119: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Turku. References: Eronen (1974); Eronen et al. (1982, 1995, 2001); Glückert (1976); Glückert et al. (1992); Rosentau et al. (2021).

6.6.3 North Sea

Figure 120: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Belgium. References: Denys and Baeteman (1995); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 121: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Bremerhaven. References: Behre et al. (1975); Behre (2003, 2007); Behre and Kučan (1999); Brandt (1980, 1991); Ey (1995); Haarnagel (1979); Hanisch (1980); Körber-Grohne (1967); Ludwig et al. (1981); Preuss (1979); Schmid (1994); Schütte (1939); Sindowski (1969); Strahl (2002a,b); Streif (1981, 1984, 1985, 1986); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 122: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Central Netherlands. References: Bennema (1954); Jelgersma (1961); Louwe Kooijmans (1976); Makaske et al. (2003); Roeleveld and Gotjé (1993); van de Plassche (1982); van de Plassche et al. (2005); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 123: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Dogger Bank. References: Behre (2003, 2007); Behre and Menke (1969); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 124: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Elbe. References: Bantelmann (1960, 1966, 1975); Bantelmann et al. (1984); Behre (2003, 2007); Behre et al. (1979); Brandt (1980); Higelke et al. (1984); Linke (1982); Meier (2001a,b); Menke (1976, 1988); Rohde (1975); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 125: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: German Bight. References: Behre (2003, 2007); Ludwig et al. (1979); Menke (1996); Streif et al. (1983); Vink et al. (2007).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 126: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Ho Bugt. References: Gehrels et al. (2006).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 127: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Langeoog. References: Barckhausen (1969); Behre (2003, 2007); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 128: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Limfjord. References: Jessen et al. (2019); Nielsen (2010, 2013); Petersen (1975, 1981, 1985, 1998); Petersen and von Platen-Hallermund (2018).

Figure 129: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Netherlands Wadden Sea. References: Griede (1978); Jelgersma (1961); Louwe Kooijmans (1976); van de Plassche (1982); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 130: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Norderney. References: Barckhausen (1984); Behre (1970, 2003, 2007); Brandt (1980); Freund and Streif (2000); Haarnagel (1957, 1969, 1980); Reinhardt (1965); Scheder et al. (2019, 2022); Streif (1986); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 131: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Oyster Ground. References: Behre and Irion (1984); Behre (2003); Jelgersma (1979); Kiden et al. (2002); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 132: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Rotterdam. References: Bennema (1954); Berendsen et al. (2007); Hijma and Cohen (2010, 2019); Hijma et al. (2009); Jelgersma (1961); Kiden (1989, 1995); Louwe Kooijmans (1976); Louwe Kooijmans and van de Velde (1980); Slupik et al. (2013); van de Plassche (1982, 1995); van de Plassche et al. (2010); van Heteren et al. (2002); Vink et al. (2007); Vos (1992, 2013); Vos and Cohen (2014); Vos et al. (2010, 2011, 2015).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 133: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Southern Bight. References: Jelgersma (1961); Kiden et al. (2002); Vink et al. (2007).

6.6.4 Skagerrak - Kattegat

Figure 134: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Asa. References: Mörner (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Figure 135: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Bohuslan. References: Persson (1973); Rosentau et al. (2021).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 136: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Goteborg. References: Mörner (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 137: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Halmstad. References: Mörner (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 138: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Kattegat. References: Bendixen et al. (2017); Bennike et al. (2000); Christiansen et al. (1993); Jensen et al. (2002); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 139: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Kieler Bucht. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Bennike et al. (2004); Rosentau et al. (2021).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 140: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Laesøe. References: Hansen (1977); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 141: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Lillebaelt. References: Andersen (2013); Bennike and Jensen (2011); Krog (1979); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021); Skaarup and Grøn (2004); Tauber (1966).

Figure 142: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Samsø Belt. References: Fischer (2005); Hede et al. (2015); Jensen and Bennike (2009); Petersen (1993); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rahbek and Rasmussen (1994); Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021); Sander et al. (2015).

Figure 143: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Storebaelt. References: Bennike et al. (2004); Christensen et al. (1997); Hede (2003); Krog (1979); Petersen (1978); Rosentau et al. (2021); Winn et al. (1986).

Figure 144: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Copenhagen. References: Bennike et al. (2012, 2017); Christensen (1982, 2014); Fischer (1993); Rasmussen (1992); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 145: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Treoa Moellebugt. References: Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 146: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Vendsyssel Thy. References: Aaris-Sørensen and Petersen (1984); Christensen and Nielsen (2008); Knudsen (1978); Krog and Tauber (1974); Petersen (1991); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Richardt (1996); Rosentau et al. (2021).

6.6.5 South Baltic

Figure 147: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Achterwasser. References: Hoffmann et al. (2009); Lampe and Janke (2004); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 148: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Arkona Basin East. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Jensen et al. (1997); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 149: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Arkona Basin West. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Jensen et al. (1997); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 150: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Baltic South. References: Bennike and Lemke (2001); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 151: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Baltic Southwest. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998, 2013); Nielsen et al. (2004); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 152: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Blekinge. References: Berglund (1964, 1971); Hansson (2018); Hansson et al. (2019); Liljegren (1970); Nylander (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021); Yu et al. (2003, 2005, 2007).

Figure 153: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Curonian Spit. References: Rosentau et al. (2021); Sergeev et al. (2015).

Figure 154: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Fakse Bugt. References: Bennike and Jensen (1995, 1998); Jensen and Stecher (1992); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 155: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Havang. References: Berglund (1971); Hansson (2018); Hansson et al. (2018a,b); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 156: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Lithuania. References: Bitinas et al. (2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2017); Damušytė (2011); Gelumbauskaitė (2009); Girininkas and Žulkus (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021); Trimonis et al. (2007); Žulkus and Girininkas (2012).

Figure 157: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Lubeck. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Bennike and Lemke (2001); Harders et al. (2005); Heinrich et al. (2018); Jensen et al. (1997, 2002); Lampe et al. (2010); Rosentau et al. (2021); Winn et al. (1986).

Figure 158: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Ostergotland. References: Persson (1979); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 159: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Rugen. References: Hoffmann et al. (2009); Lampe et al. (2010); Naumann and Lampe (2011); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 160: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Salt Meadows. References: Lampe and Janke (2004); Lampe et al. (2010); Naumann and Lampe (2011); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 161: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Sodermanland. References: Robertsson (1991); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 162: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: South Vistula. References: Miotk-Szpiganowicz (2016); Miotk-Szpiganowicz and Uścińowicz (2013); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 163: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Ustka. References: Miotk-Szpiganowicz et al. (2009); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 164: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Ventspils. References: Bērziņš et al. (2016); Murniece et al. (1999); Rosentau et al. (2021); Veinbergs (1996).

Figure 165: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: West Gulf Of Gdansk. References: Rosentau et al. (2021); Uścińowicz et al. (2011, 2013).

6.7 Greenland

6.7.1 Northeast Greenland

Figure 166: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Cape Morris Jesup. References: Funder (1982); Funder et al. (2011); Ives et al. (1964); Möller et al. (2010).

Figure 167: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Danmarks Fjord. References: Bennike and Weidick (2001); Funder (1982); Funder et al. (2011); Hjort (1997); Håkansson (1982); Ives et al. (1964); Tauber (1960, 1961, 1964); Trautman (1963).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 168: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Frederick E Hyde Fjord. References: Funder (1982); Landvik et al. (2001); Weidick (1972b, 1973, 1977).

Figure 169: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Germania Land. References: Landvik (1994).

Figure 170: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Hochstetter Forland. References: Björck et al. (1994b); Hjort (1979, 1981); Håkansson (1978, 1981); Weidick (1977).

Figure 171: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Hold With Hope. References: Hjort (1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1975); Weidick (1976, 1977).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Figure 172: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Independence Fjord. References: Bennike (2002); Funder (1982); Funder and Abrahamsen (1988); Funder et al. (2011); Ives et al. (1964); Rubin and Alexander (1960); Tauber (1966); Weidick (1977).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Figure 173: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: JP Koch Fjord. References: Landvik et al. (2001).

Figure 174: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Jameson Land. References: Björck et al. (1994a); Funder (1971, 1972, 1973, 1978, 1990a); Funder and Hansen (1996); Hjort (1979); Ingólfsson et al. (1994); Weidick (1972b, 1973, 1974).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 175: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kap Clarence Wyckoff. References: Funder (1982); Funder and Abrahamsen (1988); Funder et al. (2011); Ives et al. (1964); Tauber (1964).

Figure 176: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kempes Fjord. References: Hjort (1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1973, 1974, 1976); Weidick (1977).

Figure 177: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kong Oscars Fjord. References: Hjort (1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1972, 1973, 1974, 1975, 1976); Lasca (1966); Trautman (1963); Washburn and Stuiver (1962).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 178: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Nansen land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); Kelly and Bennike (1985, 1992); Landvik et al. (2001); Weidick (1973).

Figure 179: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Nioghalvfjærdsfjorden. References: Bennike and Weidick (2001).

Figure 180: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Prinsesse Ingeborg Halvoe. References: Bennike (1997); Funder (1982); Funder and Abrahamsen (1988); Funder et al. (2011); Hjort (1997); Håkansson (1987); Ives et al. (1964); Strunk et al. (2018); Tauber (1961).

Figure 181: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Renland. References: Funder (1971); Hjort and Funder (1974).

Figure 182: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Schuchert Dal. References: Funder (1972, 1978); Funder and Hansen (1996); Hall et al. (2008, 2010); Hjort (1979); Street (1977); Weidick (1972b).

Figure 183: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Trail Oe. References: Hjort (1973, 1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1972, 1973, 1974).

Figure 184: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Young Sound. References: Bennike and Wagner (2012); Christiansen et al. (2002); Hjort (1979); Pedersen et al. (2011); Weidick (1977).

6.7.2 Northwest Greenland

Figure 185: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Bessel Fjord. References: Bennike (2002); Blake (1987); Glueder et al. (2022); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Weidick (1977).

Figure 186: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Cass Fjord. References: Bennike (2002); Blake (1987); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Weidick (1977).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 187: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Hall Land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); England (1985); Glueder et al. (2022); Kelly and Bennike (1985, 1992); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Rubin and Alexander (1960).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 188: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Inglefield Fjord. References: Blake et al. (1996); Fredskild (1985); Weidick (1976).

Figure 189: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Nordvestoe. References: Kelly et al. (1999).

Figure 190: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Thule. References: Funder (1990b); Kelly et al. (1999).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 191: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Tuttulissuaq. References: Blake (1987); Fredskild (1985).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 192: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Warming Land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); Kelly and Bennike (1985, 1992).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 193: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Wulff land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); Kelly and Bennike (1992).

6.7.3 Southeast Greenland

Figure 194: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southeast Greenland, location: Ammassalik. References: Long et al. (2008, 2011).

6.7.4 Southwest Greenland

Figure 195: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Akulliit. References: Jungner (1979); Long and Roberts (2002); Long et al. (2011); Weidick (1972b, 1974, 1976).

Figure 196: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Alluttoq Island. References: Long et al. (2006, 1999, 2011).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 197: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Equalussuit Tasiat. References: Weidick (1972b, 1974).

Figure 198: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Ikertooq Fjord. References: Ten Brink (1975); Ten Brink and Weidick (1974); van Tatenhove et al. (1996); Weidick (1972b, 1973).

Figure 199: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Ilulissat. References: Long et al. (2006, 2011); Weidick (1972b, 1973).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 200: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Itilleq. References: Long et al. (2009, 2011); Weidick (1972b).

Figure 201: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kangerluk. References: Bennike (1995); Föged (1989); Long et al. (2011); Rasch (1997); Souza et al. (2021).

Figure 202: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kangerlussuaq. References: Bierman et al. (2018); Storms et al. (2012); Ten Brink (1975); Ten Brink and Weidick (1974); van Tatenhove et al. (1996); Weidick (1972a,b, 1973).

Figure 203: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kannala. References: Jungner (1979); Long and Roberts (2003); Long et al. (2003, 2011); Weidick (1974, 1976).

Figure 204: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kapisillit. References: Fredskild (1973, 1983); Larsen et al. (2014); McGovern et al. (1996); Weidick (1968, 1972a, 1975, 1976); Weidick et al. (2012).

Figure 205: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Maniitsoq. References: Weidick (1973).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 206: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Nanortalik. References: Bennike et al. (2002); Long et al. (2011); Sparrenbom et al. (2006b).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Figure 207: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Nuuk. References: Berglund (2003); Fredskild (1983); Hinnerson-Berglund (2004); Larsen et al. (2014, 2017); Weidick (1973, 1976).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 208: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Paamiut. References: Woodroffe et al. (2014).

Figure 209: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Qaqortoq. References: Bennike et al. (2002); Bierman et al. (2018); Fredh (2008); Long et al. (2011); Randsalu (2008); Sparrenbom et al. (2006a); Weidick (1975).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 210: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Qeqertarsuatsiaat. References: Larsen et al. (2014); Weidick (1975).

Figure 211: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Sisimiut. References: Bennike et al. (2011); Long et al. (2011); Weidick (1972b, 1973).

Figure 212: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Tasiussarsuaq. References: Lasher et al. (2020).

6.8 North America Arctic

6.8.1 Hudson Bay

Figure 213: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Churchill. References: Anderson and Hodgetts (2007); Andrews and Falconer (1969); Blake (1982, 1988); Dyck and Fyles (1964); Hodgetts (2007); Kuhry (2008); Lowdon and Blake (1973); Lowdon et al. (1971); Meyer (1970); Morlan et al. (2000); Nash (1972); Simon et al. (2016); Vacchi et al. (2018); Wagner (1967).

Figure 214: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: East James Bay. References: Beaulieu-Audy et al. (2009); Farrand (1962); Hardy (1976); Pendea et al. (2010); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 215: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Inukjuak. References: Andrews and Falconer (1969); Andrews and Short (1983); Buckley and Willis (1970); Harington (2003); Lauriol and Gray (1997); Lemieux et al. (2011); Lowdon and Blake (1968); Saint-Laurent and Filion (1992); Vacchi et al. (2018); Wagner (1967).

Figure 216: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Ivujivik. References: Daigneault (2008); Harington (2003); Martindale et al. (2020); Matthews (1966, 1967); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018); Wagner (1967).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 217: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Kivalliq. References: Aylsworth et al. (1981); Blake (1983, 1986, 1988); Dyck and Fyles (1962); Dyck et al. (1966); Lowdon and Blake (1970); Lowdon and Blake (1979); McNeely and Atkinson (1995); Morrison (1989); Ridler (1974); Rutherford et al. (1973, 1979); Simon et al. (2014, 2016); Vacchi et al. (2018); Walton et al. (1961).

Figure 218: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Umiujaq. References: Allard and Seguin (1985); Allard and Tremblay (1983a,b); Cayer (2003); Filion et al. (1991); Gajewski and Garralla (1992); Hillaire-Marcel (1976); Lajeunesse and Allard (2003); Lamarre et al. (2012); Lavoie et al. (2012); Lowdon and Blake (1980); Lowdon et al. (1967); McNeely (2006); Plumet (1974); Saulnier-Talbot and Pienitz (2001); Vacchi et al. (2018); Walcott and Craig (1975).

Figure 219: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: West James Bay. References: Bunbury et al. (2012); Dyck et al. (1965); Dyke and Peltier (2000); Glaser et al. (2004); McAndrews et al. (1982); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018); Vogel and Waterbolk (1972); Webber et al. (1970).

6.8.2 Hudson Strait

Figure 220: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Kangiqsujuaq. References: Daigneault (2008); Dyke et al. (2003); Gray et al. (1993); Gray (2001); Lauriol and Gray (1987); McNeely (2002, 2005); McNeely and Atkinson (1995); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 221: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Southern Ungava Bay. References: Gray (2001); Pienitz et al. (1991); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 222: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Sugluk. References: Bartley and Matthews (1969); Daigneault (2008); Gray et al. (1993); Gray (2001); Gray and Lauriol (1985); Kasper and Allard (2001); Lauriol and Gray (1997); Lowdon and Blake (1968); Matthews (1966); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Ricard (1989); Simon et al. (2016); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 223: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Western Ungava Bay. References: Gray et al. (1980, 1993); Lauriol and Gray (1987); Lauriol et al. (1979); Løken (1978); Simon et al. (2016); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9 North America Atlantic

6.9.1 Eastern United States

Figure 224: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Eastern Shore. References: Engelhart and Horton (2012); Engelhart et al. (2009); Finkelstein and Ferland (1987); Newman and Rusnak (1965); van de Plassche (1990).

Figure 225: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Inner Chesapeake. References: Cinqumani et al. (1982); Colman et al. (2002); Engelhart and Horton (2012).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Figure 226: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Inner Delaware. References: Belknap (1975); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Kraft (1976); Leorri et al. (2006); Marx (1981); Nikitina et al. (2000); Ramsey and Baxter (1996); Rogers and Pizzuto (1994).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Figure 227: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Northern North Carolina. References: Emery et al. (1967); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Horton et al. (2009); Kemp (2009); Mallinson et al. (2005); Sears (1973); Stanton (2008).

Figure 228: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Northern South Carolina. References: Cinqemani et al. (1982); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Gayes et al. (1992).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Figure 229: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Outer Delaware. References: Belknap (1975); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Fletcher et al. (1993); Nikitina et al. (2000); Ramsey and Baxter (1996).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Figure 230: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Southern North Carolina. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Culver et al. (2007); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Horton et al. (2009); Kemp (2009); Spaur and Snyder (1999).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 231: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Southern South Carolina. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Engelhart and Horton (2012).

6.9.2 Labrador

Figure 232: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Hamilton Inlet. References: Fitzhugh (1972, 1975); Lowdon and Blake (1975); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 233: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Lake Melville. References: Awadallah and Batterson (1990); Batterson (1996); Jordan (1975); King (1985); Liverman (1997); Lowdon and Blake (1975); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 234: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Nain. References: Clark and Fitzhugh (1990); Martindale et al. (2020); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Figure 235: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Torngat. References: Dyke et al. (2003); Evans and Rogerson (1988); Lowdon and Blake (1975); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Savoie and Gangloff (1980); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9.3 Maritimes

Figure 236: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Anticosti Island. References: Dubois et al. (1988); Lavoie and Filion (2001); Painchaud et al. (1984); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 237: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Cape Breton. References: Blake and Lowdon (1976); Miller and Livingstone (1993); Shaw et al. (2009); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 238: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Chaleur Bay. References: McNeely and Brennan (2005); Rampton et al. (1984); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 239: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Cumberland. References: Dalrymple and Zaitlin (1994); Scott and Greenberg (1983); Shaw et al. (2010); Stea and Wightman (1987); Stuckenrath et al. (1966); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 240: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Forestville. References: Dietrich et al. (2017); Dionne (1996, 2001b); Dionne and Occhietti (1996); Dionne et al. (2004); Dubois et al. (1988); Martindale et al. (2020); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 241: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Halifax. References: Blake (1988); Edgecombe et al. (1999); Gehrels et al. (2004, 2005); Miller et al. (1982); Scott and Medioli (1982); Scott et al. (1995); Shaw et al. (1993); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 242: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Magdalen Islands. References: Barnett et al. (2017); Dredge et al. (1992); Rémillard et al. (2016, 2017); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 243: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Passamaquoddy Bay. References: Blake (1984); Gehrels et al. (2004); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely (2005); Miller (1990); Nicks (1991); Rampton et al. (1984); Seaman (2004); Stea and Mott (1998); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 244: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Prince Edward Island. References: Kranck (1972); McCallum and Wittenberg (1965); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Ogden and Hart (1976); Scott et al. (1981, 1987); Stea and Mott (1989); Vacchi et al. (2018); Walton et al. (1961).

Figure 245: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Quebec City. References: Bhiry et al. (2000); Brodeur and Allard (1985); Dionne (1988, 1997, 1998); Filion (1987); Govare and Gangloff (1989); McNeely (2006); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Occhietti et al. (2001); Parent and Occhietti (1988); Samson et al. (1977); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 246: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Rimouski. References: Blake and Lowdon (1976); Dionne (1990, 1999, 2001a, 2005); Dionne and Coll (1995); Dyck and Fyles (1963); Harington (2003); Héту (1998); Héту and Bail (1996); Héту (1994); Locat (1977); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 247: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Sable Island. References: Amos and Miller (1990); Scott et al. (1984, 1989); Vacchi et al. (2018).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 248: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Shelburne. References: Blake (1983); Lowdon and Blake (1970); Scott and Greenberg (1983); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9.4 Newfoundland

Figure 249: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Avalon Peninsula. References: Catto et al. (2000); Daly et al. (2007); MacPherson (1996); McNeely (2006); Shaw and Forbes (1995); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 250: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Bay Of Islands. References: Brookes et al. (1985); Brookes and Stevens (1985); Daly et al. (2007); Grant (1994); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 251: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Great Northern Peninsula. References: Bell et al. (2005); Grant (1992, 1994); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Jorgensen (1993); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Nydal (1989); Tuck (1971); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 252: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Notre Dame Bay. References: Blake (1983); Daly et al. (2007); Dyck and Fyles (1963); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Scott et al. (1991); Shaw and Edwardson (1994); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 253: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Port Aux Basques. References: Bell et al. (2003); Blake (1988); Brookes et al. (1985); Daly et al. (2007); Dyke et al. (2003); Forbes et al. (1993); Kemp et al. (2017); Lowdon and Blake (1980); Lowdon et al. (1971); McNeely (2002); McNeely and Atkinson (1995); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and Jorgensen (1992, 1993); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Shaw and Forbes (1987, 1995); Shaw and Potter (2015); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9.5 Northeastern United States

Figure 254: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Connecticut. References: Bloom (1963); Cinquemani et al. (1982); Donnelly et al. (2004); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Nydick et al. (1995); Redfield and Rubin (1962); van de Plassche (1991); van de Plassche et al. (1989, 1998, 2002).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 255: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Eastern Maine. References: Belknap et al. (1989); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Gehrels (1999); Gehrels and Belknap (1993); Gehrels et al. (1996).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 256: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Long Island. References: Bloom (1963); Cinquemani et al. (1982); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Pardi and Newman (1980); Pardi et al. (1984); Redfield (1967); Redfield and Rubin (1962).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 257: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: New Jersey. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Donnelly et al. (2001); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Miller et al. (2009); Pardi et al. (1984); Psuty (1986); Stuiver and Daddario (1963).

Figure 258: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: New York. References: Engelhart and Horton (2012); Olson and Broecker (1961); Pardi et al. (1984); Slagter et al. (2006).

Figure 259: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Northern Massachusetts. References: Donnelly (2006); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Kaye and Barghoorn (1964); Kirwan et al. (2011); Newman et al. (1980); Oldale et al. (1993); Redfield (1967); Redfield and Rubin (1962).

Figure 260: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Southern Maine. References: Barnhardt et al. (1995); Belknap et al. (1989); Bloom (1963); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Gehrels et al. (1996, 2002); Kelley et al. (1992, 1995).

Figure 261: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Southern Massachusetts. References: Emery et al. (1967); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Gutierrez et al. (2003); Oldale and O'Hara (1980); Redfield (1967); Redfield and Rubin (1962); Stuiver et al. (1963).

6.10 Pacific Islands

6.10.1 French Polynesia

Figure 262: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Mururoa. References: Camoin et al. (2001); Hibbert et al. (2016).

Figure 263: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Tahiti. References: Bard et al. (1996, 2010); Deschamps et al. (2012); Hibbert et al. (2016).

6.10.2 Melansia

Figure 264: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Melansia, location: Vanuatu. References: Cabioch et al. (2003); Cutler et al. (2004); Hibbert et al. (2016).

6.11 Proxy Based Sea Level

6.11.1 Red Sea

Figure 265: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Red Sea, location: Bab-el-Mandeb (Red Sea $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Proxy). References: Grant et al. (2012, 2014).

6.12 South Asia

6.12.1 Bay of Bengal

Figure 266: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Bay of Bengal, location: Ganges Delta. References: Wiedicke et al. (1999).

6.13 Southeast Asia

6.13.1 Java Sea

Figure 267: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: Belitung Island. References: Mann et al. (2019); Meltzner et al. (2017).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$) ■ Index point ($>10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 268: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: Central Java. References: Azmy et al. (2010); Mann et al. (2019).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 269: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: South Sulawesi. References: de Klerk (1982); Mann et al. (2016, 2019); Tjia et al. (1972).

6.13.2 Papua New Guinea

Figure 270: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Papua New Guinea, location: Huon Peninsula. References: Chappell and Polach (1991); Cutler et al. (2003); Edwards et al. (1993); Hibbert et al. (2016); Mann et al. (2019).

6.13.3 South China Sea

Figure 271: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South China Sea, location: Xisha Islands. References: Yu et al. (2022).

6.13.4 Sundaland

Figure 272: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Ca Na. References: Mann et al. (2019); Statterger et al. (2013).

Figure 273: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Chao Phraya. References: Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019); Sinsakul (1992); Somboon (1988); Somboon and Thiramongkol (1992).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
 - Index point ($>10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 274: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: East Malay Peninsula. References: Mann et al. (2019); Parham et al. (2014); Tjia and Fujii (1992).

Figure 275: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Mekong Delta. References: Hanebuth et al. (2012); Mann et al. (2019); Statterger et al. (2013); Tamura et al. (2007, 2009).

Figure 276: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Phuket. References: Mann et al. (2019); Scheffers et al. (2012); Scoffin and Le Tissier (1998).

Figure 277: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Southeast Malay Peninsula. References: Hassan (2001); Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019); Tjia and Fujii (1992); Tjia et al. (1983).

Figure 278: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Strait Of Malacca. References: Bird et al. (2007, 2010); Geyh et al. (1979); Hassan (2001); Hesp et al. (1998); Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019); Tjia and Fujii (1992).

Figure 279: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Sunda Shelf. References: Hanebuth et al. (2000, 2003, 2009).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 280: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Thale Noi. References: Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
 - Index point ($> 10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 281: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Vietnam Shelf. References: Hanebuth et al. (2000).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 282: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: West Malay Peninsula. References: Mann et al. (2019); Tjia and Fujii (1992); Tjia et al. (1972).

7 MIS 3 and 4 – Sea level Indicators and Proxies

MIS 3 is an interstadial period that stretches between about 55 and 27 kyr before present. MIS 4 is a glacial period when the ice sheets significantly expanded in North America and Europe, between about 70 and 55 kyr. There are few sea level proxies from this time interval for three main reasons. First, such deposits are hard to date, because the material is near or beyond the limits of radiocarbon dating. Second, the geological evidence in many areas was eroded by the subsequent rise in sea level during the MIS 1 and 2 deglaciation. As a result, many of the proxies are only preserved in places where there is a substantial tectonic uplift rate. Third, relative sea level during MIS 3 and 4 likely never exceeded -30 m, so the deposits are likely below the depth limit of most coring survey methods.

7.1 Antarctica

7.1.1 East Antarctica

Figure 283: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Langhovde. References: Igarashi et al. (1995a,b); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Maemoku et al. (1997); Miura et al. (1998).

Figure 284: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Larsemann Hills. References: Hodgson et al. (2009); Ishiwa et al. (2021).

Figure 285: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Ongul Islands. References: Hirakawa and Sawagaki (1998); Igarashi et al. (1995a,b); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Miura et al. (1998).

Figure 286: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Rauer Group. References: Berg et al. (2010a, 2016); Ishiwa et al. (2021).

7.2 Australia

7.2.1 Northern Australia

Figure 287: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf. References: Ishiwa et al. (2019); Yokoyama et al. (2000).

Figure 288: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Ishiwa *et al.* 2019 interpretation). References: Ishiwa *et al.* (2019); Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

Figure 289: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Yokoyama *et al.* 2000 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

7.2.2 Queensland

Figure 290: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Cairns. References: Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2013); Yokoyama et al. (2018).

Figure 291: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Hydrographers Passage. References: Yokoyama et al. (2018).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
 - Index point ($>10\text{m}$)

Figure 292: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Townsville. References: Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2013); Ohlenbusch (1991).

7.3 Caribbean

7.3.1 Lesser Antilles

Figure 293: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Lesser Antilles, location: Barbados. References: Abdul et al. (2016); Fairbanks (1988); Peltier and Fairbanks (2006).

7.4 East Asia

7.4.1 Ryukyu Islands

Figure 294: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Ryukyu Islands, location: Kikaijima (1.9 mm/yr uplift rate). References: Konishi et al. (1974); Omura (1988); Omura and Konishi (1970); Omura et al. (1985, 2000); Sasaki et al. (2004).

Figure 295: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Ryukyu Islands, location: Kikaijima (2.1 mm/yr uplift rate). References: Konishi et al. (1974); Omura (1988); Omura and Konishi (1970); Omura et al. (1985, 2000); Sasaki et al. (2004).

7.4.2 Sea of Japan - East Sea

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 296: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sea of Japan - East Sea, location: Tsushima-Korea Strait. References: Park et al. (2000).

7.4.3 Yellow Sea

Figure 297: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Yellow Sea, location: South Bohai Sea. References: Liu et al. (2009); Pico et al. (2016).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 298: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Yellow Sea, location: Yellow Sea. References: Liu et al. (2010); Pico et al. (2016); Wang et al. (2014).

7.5 Greenland

7.5.1 Northeast Greenland

Figure 299: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Cape Morris Jesup. References: Funder et al. (2011).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 300: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kap Clarence Wyckoff. References: Funder et al. (2011).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Figure 301: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Nansen land. References: Landvik et al. (2001).

7.6 North America Atlantic

7.6.1 Eastern United States

Figure 302: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Eastern Shore. References: Engelhart and Horton (2012); Mixon et al. (1982); Parham et al. (2013); Scott (2006).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 303: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Northern North Carolina. References: Culver et al. (2011); Mallinson et al. (2008); Parham et al. (2013); Pico et al. (2017); Scott (2006).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 304: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Southern North Carolina. References: Best (2010); Moore (2009); Parham et al. (2013); Pico et al. (2017).

7.7 Pacific Islands

7.7.1 French Polynesia

Figure 305: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Mururoa. References: Camoin et al. (2001); Hibbert et al. (2016).

Figure 306: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Tahiti. References: Hibbert et al. (2016); Thomas et al. (2009).

7.7.2 Melansia

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 307: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Melansia, location: Vanuatu. References: Cabioch and Ayliffe (2001).

7.8 Proxy Based Sea Level

7.8.1 Java Sea

Figure 308: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: Karimata Strait (Sulu Sea $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Proxy). References: Weiss et al. (2022).

7.8.2 Red Sea

Figure 309: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Red Sea, location: Bab-el-Mandeb (Red Sea $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Proxy). References: Grant et al. (2012, 2014).

7.9 South Asia

7.9.1 Bay of Bengal

Figure 310: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Bay of Bengal, location: Ganges Delta. References: Wiedicke et al. (1999).

7.10 Southeast Asia

7.10.1 Papua New Guinea

Figure 311: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Papua New Guinea, location: Huon Peninsula. References: Chappell et al. (1996); Cutler et al. (2003); Hibbert et al. (2016); Yokoyama et al. (2001).

Figure 312: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Papua New Guinea, location: Huon Peninsula (Interpretation by de Gelder *et al.*). References: Chappell (2002); Chappell *et al.* (1996); de Gelder *et al.* (2022).

7.10.2 South China Sea

Figure 313: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South China Sea, location: Xisha Islands. References: Yu et al. (2022).

7.10.3 Sundaland

Figure 314: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Berhala Strait. References: Geyh et al. (1979); Mann et al. (2019).

Figure 315: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Chao Phraya. References: Mann et al. (2019); Tanabe et al. (2003).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 316: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Mekong Delta. References: Mann et al. (2019); Ta et al. (2002).

Figure 317: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Strait Of Malacca. References: Geyh et al. (1979); Mann et al. (2019).

Figure 318: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Sunda Shelf. References: Hanebuth et al. (2003); Steinke et al. (2003).

Figure 319: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Vietnam Shelf. References: Schimanski and Stattegger (2005).

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